

Sea-level rise and coastal flooding

Understanding the risks

The National Tidal and Sea Level Facility

Rising sea levels and climate change, which may affect the frequency and severity of storm conditions around our coastline, have profound implications for coastal protection and marine management. The National Tidal and Sea Level Facility (NTSLF) is the UK centre of excellence for monitoring sea level, modelling tides and storm surges, and analysing sea-level extremes. We advise policy-makers, planners and coastal engineers on the impacts of sea-level rise.

tide gauges coastal erosion

Sea-level expertise

Global sea level is expected to rise by between 20 and 90cm by the year 2100. This will change the frequency and extent of coastal flooding. Managing the risk and developing effective forecasting systems demand total expertise in the science behind sea-level rise, tides, storm surges and inundation.

The NTSLF is based at the Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory in Liverpool. Proudman is a world-leading authority in global and regional sea-level processes.

With partners in top research universities, coastal engineering consultancies and the Met Office, we provide unique expertise in sea-level measurement, computer modelling of tides and storm surges, and the statistical estimation of extreme sea levels.

Our work is of strategic importance to government, local authorities, the public and the scientific community. We ensure that scientific advances in sea-level prediction and coastal flood forecasting are communicated rapidly to all stakeholders. We also provide crucial input on waves and sea level to the UK Marine Climate Change Impacts Partnership and to international groups such as the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC).

Top: Cliff erosion at Happisburgh, Norfolk.

Above: A storm hits Blackpool. John Giles/PA News

computer mod

Left: Sea Palling, Norfolk, February 1953. Eastern Daily Press

Below: Tsunami damage in the Solomon Islands. Roger Wheatley/AusAID

Storm surges and coastal flood forecasting

Storm surges are temporary increases in sea level caused by low atmospheric pressure combined with strong winds. When winter storms pass over the UK, surges can raise sea level by 2-3m. This natural hazard is made worse by the fact that the UK has some of the world's largest tidal ranges. A severe North Sea storm surge in 1953 killed 307 people in Britain.

Effective warning systems for surge prediction are essential to protect coastal communities and minimise economic loss.

Accurate advanced forecasts helped minimise damage and disruption on 9 November 2007 when the worst storm surge in 20 years struck the east coast of Britain. Computer models developed by NTSLF are a central component of the warning system. Twelve hours before the storm surge struck, the predictions from these models were accurate to better than ten per cent.

Advanced warning

NTSLF scientists and our colleagues at the Met Office are constantly improving the accuracy of computer models used for operational coastal flood forecasting. The models run four times a day and make predictions up to two days ahead. We have recently developed an ensemble prediction system to provide increased forecast confidence.

We also develop computer models to investigate the characteristics of storm surges and extreme sea levels in future climate scenarios, and to assess tsunami risk in the UK and elsewhere.

Storm surge heights from the operational model at 0600 on 9 November 2007.

Accuracy of model predictions during the North Sea storm surge of 9 November 2007.

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Precision measurements

Long-term records from NTSLF tide gauges confirm the global picture of sea-level changes over the past century, with sea level at Newlyn rising by 1.8mm a year since 1915. Accurately assessing sea-level change is complicated by post-glacial rebound – the slow adjustment of land masses that were loaded by glaciers during the last ice age. To distinguish vertical land movement from sea-level rise, our scientists have worked with the University of Nottingham to develop a monitoring network based on GPS technology.

Our engineers have developed advanced communications systems to transmit sea-level information from anywhere in the world by satellite, and over the internet. For coastal flood warning around the UK, our systems deliver data from all gauges to forecasters within 15 minutes. From our national data archive we derive the estimates of extreme sea-level heights necessary for planning coastal defences.

National and international tide-gauge network

The NTSLF manages precision tide gauges at 44 sites around the UK. We also monitor sea level at strategic sites in the south Atlantic as part of our contribution towards international climate change research, and across other British Overseas Territories. Following the 2004 Boxing Day tsunami, scientists at NTSLF helped to develop and install a tide-gauge network around Africa to better monitor sea levels in the Indian Ocean.

Annual sea level at Newlyn (1915-2004).

Surge at Lowestoft

— model forecast
+ observations
◆ time of high water

Sea level networks

UK Tide Gauge Network

About the UK network
The UK National Tide Gauge Network, run by the Tide Gauge Inspectorate, records tidal elevations at 44 locations around the UK coast. Find out about instruments, tide gauges and systems - [More]

Operational status
This shows the latest information regarding tide gauge operations e.g. notes on gauge problems and dates of maintenance - [More]

Real/Near-real time data display
Use the links below to view the latest measurements from gauges on the UK Tide Gauge Network

RT - Click red links below to view real/near real-time data from each tide gauge
ST - Click orange links below to find out about site information for each tide gauge location
XS - Click blue links below to view highest and lowest surge values for entire history of site

England - South
 Avonmouth RT | ST | XS
 Bournemouth RT | ST | XS
 Dover RT | ST | XS
 Hinkley RT | ST | XS
 Iffracombe RT | ST | XS
 Newlyn RT | ST | XS
 Plymouth RT | ST | XS
 Portsmouth RT | ST | XS
 St. Mary's RT | ST | XS
 Weymouth RT | ST | XS

England - East
 Cromer RT | ST | XS
 Felixstowe RT | ST | XS
 Harwich RT | ST | XS
 Immingham RT | ST | XS
 Lowestoft RT | ST | XS
 North Shields RT | ST | XS
 Sneeshess RT | ST | XS
 Whitby RT | ST | XS

Scotland
 Aberdeen RT | ST | XS
 Kintlochberrie RT | ST | XS
 Leith RT | ST | XS
 Lerwick RT | ST | XS
 Millport RT | ST | XS
 Moray Firth RT | ST | XS
 Port Ellen RT | ST | XS
 Portpatrick RT | ST | XS
 Spornroy RT | ST | XS
 Tobermory RT | ST | XS
 Wick RT | ST | XS

Wales
 Barmouth RT | ST | XS
 Fishguard RT | ST | XS
 Holyhead RT | ST | XS
 Llandudno RT | ST | XS
 Milford Haven RT | ST | XS
 Mumbles RT | ST | XS
 Newport RT | ST | XS

Channel Islands
 St. Helier RT | ST | XS

Isle of Man
 St. Erin RT | ST | XS

LIVERPOOL (ALFRED DOCK)
 Datum : Chart Datum

GMT	Time	Height	Time	Height	Time	Height		
1	0406	0.20	16	0402	2.17	16	0408	1.28
	0408	0.20	16	0412	2.20		0410	1.28
2	0410	0.19	17	0417	2.24	17	0412	1.28
	0412	0.18	17	0421	2.26		0414	1.27
3	0414	0.17	18	0428	2.30	18	0418	1.26
	0416	0.16	18	0432	2.32		0420	1.25
4	0418	0.15	19	0439	2.34	19	0424	1.24
	0420	0.14	19	0443	2.36		0426	1.23
5	0422	0.13	20	0450	2.38	20	0430	1.22
	0424	0.12	20	0454	2.40		0432	1.21
6	0426	0.11	21	0501	2.41	21	0436	1.20
	0428	0.10	21	0505	2.43		0438	1.19
7	0430	0.09	22	0512	2.44	22	0442	1.18
	0432	0.08	22	0516	2.46		0444	1.17

Data and products

The NTSLF website (www.pol.ac.uk/ntslf) provides:

- real-time displays of UK sea levels
- forecasts from the storm-surge model
- measurements from the south Atlantic and Gibraltar
- conversions between commonly used datums
- extreme high- and low-water information
- harmonic analysis tools

We maintain the national archive of quality controlled tide-gauge data. These data are available free of charge from the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC).

Also available from the POL Applications Team are tidal predictions for over 700 coastal locations, customised tide tables and offshore tidal-prediction software.

John Gillies/PA News

forecasting modelling

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